

Study the Role of First Trimester Uterine Artery Doppler in Prediction of Pre-Eclampsia and Its Feto-Maternal OutcomeAnshika Agarwal¹, Puneet Agrawal², Ayush Agarwal³, Diksha Sharma⁴¹MBBS, MS OBGY, Senior Resident, Dept of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Government Medical College Datia (MP)²MBBS, MD, Government Medical College, Datia (MP)³MBBS MD, Muzaffarnagar Medical College, Muzaffarnagar⁴MBBS, MS OBGY, Muzaffarnagar Medical College, Muzaffarnagar

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** To analyze first-trimester uterine artery doppler to predict pre-eclampsia for early detection and diagnosis of PIH.**Objective:** (1). To evaluate the usefulness of uterine artery doppler screening in first-trimester to predict the risk for preeclampsia. (2). To know the outcome of pregnancy and its relation with the uterine artery Doppler indices. (3). To study effect on maternal mortality and morbidity of early prediction of pre-eclampsia to prevent maternal mortality and morbidity.**Methodology:** This hospital based prospective longitudinal study was carried out at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Muzaffarnagar Medical college, Muzaffarnagar for a duration of 18 months. A total of 100 cases were enrolled from Gynae OPD, presenting for a routine prenatal ultrasound examination by simple random sampling technique. Transabdominal Doppler Ultrasound scan was done at 11 to 14 weeks. The basic parameter monitored in our study was the pulsatility index = peak systolic velocity - end diastolic velocity/mean (PI = S-D/Mean) and the presence of bilateral notch in the uterine artery.**Results:** Overall mean PI among the study subjects was 1.81±1.85, on Right Uterine Artery it was 1.77±1.88 and on Left Uterine Artery it was 1.84±1.82. There were 28 subjects (28%) with abnormal PI i.e., ≥1.5 and remaining 72 (72%) had normal PI (<1.5). In 72 subjects with PI <1.5, one subject (1.39%) each Gestational hypertension, Oligohydramnios and Stillbirth; 2 females (2.78%) had Preeclampsia; and Fetal growth restriction (FGR) was present in 5 subjects (6.94). There was statistically significant difference (p<0.01) in Gestational hypertension, Preeclampsia, Oligohydramnios and FGR when two groups were compared.**Conclusion:** According to the results of the current study, uterine artery color doppler is a useful and non-invasive method for predicting preeclampsia at term in healthy pregnancies.**Keywords:** Uterine Artery Doppler, Pre-Eclampsia.

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Introduction

According to ACOG (2018 guideline)-Preeclampsia is defined as a new onset of hypertension (>140/90 mmHg) appearing after 20 weeks of gestation and accompanied by proteinuria (>0.3 g/24 h) [1]. It affects 5-10% of pregnancies worldwide and 4.6% of pregnancies in India. Along with hemorrhage and infection, it forms a member of the deadly triad and is the leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality (14% globally and 29.54% in India) [2]. The primary cause of PE is attributed to relatively under-perfused/hypoxic/ischemic placenta, probably due to the abnormal development of placental vasculature early in the duration of pregnancy. The early diagnosis of PE during pregnancy is needed

to plan appropriate treatment and the monitoring of management.

Pre-eclampsia is a major cause of severe maternal morbidity. The disease causes multi-organ connectivity due to systemic vasospasm associated with endothelial lesions and microcirculatory alterations at the level of the central nervous system, kidney, lung, liver, retina, and other organs. This can lead to multiple organ failure and sequelae [3]. Maternal complications of pre-eclampsia include coagulopathy, renal and hepatic failure, and stroke.

Pre-eclampsia is characterized by abnormal placenta formation, which results in inadequate

uteroplacental blood flow. This has led to the idea of using Doppler ultrasonography providing a non-invasive method for screening to assess the velocity of uterine artery blood flow as part of routine investigation. With the use of ultrasonography (U/S) for predicting/screening PE, it was observed that PE due to defective placentation causes an incomplete transformation of spiral arteries [4]. A lesion of placental villi and vascular histopathology is four to seven times more commonly seen in PE as compared to non-PE pregnancies [5]. They are linked to an increase in resistance to the flow of the uterine artery. Persistence of a diastolic notch (beyond 24 weeks' gestation) or abnormal flow velocity ratios have been associated with inadequate trophoblast invasion [6].

In normal pregnancy, the fetoplacental circulation acts as a low resistance system unit. Thus, blood velocity waveforms in umbilical artery shows continuous forward flow throughout the cardiac cycle. But impaired placental perfusion, which is one of the hallmarks of preeclampsia, can be assessed by measuring flow waveform ratios or by detecting diastolic notching of uterine and umbilical vessels. Overall, first trimester Doppler interrogation of the uterine artery performs better in the prediction of early onset than late onset preeclampsia [7].

Doppler examination of the uterine arteries especially in first trimester is a non-invasive tool that can be used to indirectly assess trophoblast development and uteroplacental perfusion. Several studies have been performed to assess the validity of second-trimester uterine artery Doppler examination as a screening tool for pre-eclampsia.

Material and Methods

This hospital based prospective longitudinal study was carried out at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Muzaffarnagar Medical college, Muzaffarnagar for a duration of 18 months. A total of 100 cases were enrolled from Gynae OPD, presenting for a routine prenatal ultrasound examination at 11 – 14 weeks by simple random sampling technique.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Singleton pregnancy
2. All pregnancies with correct LMP who were sure of dates
3. Pregnancy 11- 14 weeks
4. Patients who gave informed written consent

Exclusion Criteria

1. Pregnancy <11 weeks

2. Pregnancy > 14 weeks
3. Any Congenital anomaly
4. Chronic inflammatory disease
5. Multiple pregnancies
6. Foetal abnormalities
7. Patients who did not give consent

Demographic and clinical risk factors were observed: - maternal age, address, socio-economic status, occupation, religion, gestational age, LMP EDD, parity index G P L A, Chief complaints. Detailed history was taken. Investigation like Haemoglobin, Blood group, Random Blood sugar, Urine routine microscopy, viral markers were sent.

Transabdominal Doppler Ultrasound scan was done at 11 to 14 weeks. Ultrasonography was performed using a ECube alpinion 8 machine, equipped with a convex abdominal probe of 2.0–5.0 MHz and an endovaginal probe (4–10 MHz). As part of routine ultrasound at 11–14 weeks, a sagittal section of the cervix is obtained. Color Doppler is used to identify the uterine artery which is visualized perpendicular to iliac vessels which is traced upto the cervico-corporeal junction. Pulsed wave doppler was used to obtain uterine artery flow waveforms and the mean pulsatility index (PI) of the uterine arteries was calculated.

The basic parameter monitored in our study was the pulsatility index = peak systolic velocity - end diastolic velocity/mean (PI = S-D/Mean) and the presence of bilateral notch in the uterine artery.

For PI interpretation, we used the normative reference curves by age (first trimester 95th percentile value = 2.71). A binary logit model is used to assess whether Doppler changes (PI > 95th percentile or bilateral notch) in the first are correlated with the probability of development of preeclampsia.

A t test is used for the study of the statistical significance of coefficients. A variable is considered to be statistically significant if the value of $p < 0.05$. The predictive power of the functions used is assessed by the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristics).

Abnormal uterine artery Doppler appearance is defined as the presence of bilateral notch and/or a $PI \geq 1.5$.

The patient was followed up till delivery and the outcome was noted. Every case was followed up in the antenatal clinic for the development of complication such as pre-eclampsia according to ACOG criteria.

Results

Table 1: Mean PI and PI distribution among the 100 subjects

PI	Mean	SD
Right Uterine Artery	1.77	1.88
Left Uterine Artery	1.84	1.82
Total	1.81	1.85
PI	N	%
≥1.5 (Abnormal)	28	28
<1.5 (Normal)	72	72

Table 2: Comparison of adverse pregnancy outcomes according to PI

Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes	PI				Chi Square	p value
	>1.5		<1.5			
	N=28	%	N=72	%		
Gestational hypertension	3	10.71	1	1.39	5.49	0.024
Preeclampsia	4	14.29	2	2.78	6.11	0.022*
Eclampsia	1	3.57	0	0.00	0.92	0.67
Oligohydramnios	5	17.86	1	1.39	11.78	<0.01*
Fetal growth restriction	8	28.57	5	6.94	14.32	<0.01*
Placental abruption	1	3.57	0	0.00	0.92	0.67
Stillbirth	1	3.57	1	1.39	0.76	0.81
Mortality	1	3.57	0	0	0.92	0.67

Table 3: Neonatal outcomes among the study subjects according to PI

Neonatal Outcomes	PI				Chi Square	p value
	≥1.5		<1.5			
	N=28	%	N=72	%		
Underweight	3	10.71	0	0	5.91	0.021*
NICU Admission	5	17.86	1	1.39	6.76	0.017*
Mortality	0	0	0	0	0	1

Table 4: Diagnostic efficacy of PI to predict adverse pregnancy outcomes

Parameters	Value
Sensitivity	63.80%
Specificity	82.40%
Negative Predictive Value	60.60%
Positive Predictive Value	80.90%
Accuracy	68.2%

Discussion

Overall mean PI among the study subjects was 1.81 ± 1.85 , on Right Uterine Artery it was 1.77 ± 1.88 and on Left Uterine Artery it was 1.84 ± 1.82 . There were 28 subjects (28%) with abnormal PI i.e., ≥ 1.5 and remaining 72 (72%) had normal PI (< 1.5). These results were in accordance to findings of Jayson JA et al., (2021) [8] and Bindal J, Chugh N (2016) [9].

Gestational hypertension was present in 4 females (4%), eclampsia in 1 (1%) woman and oligohydramnios was present in 6 subjects (6%). Among 6 subjects with Pre-eclampsia, 2 had mild Pre-eclampsia and 4 had severe Pre-eclampsia. Fetal growth restriction (FGR) was present in 13 subjects, Placental abruption in one woman and stillbirth was in 2 subjects. Jayson JA et al., (2021), observed that among all the women studied, 13.2 % developed gestational hypertension, 10.29 % developed PE, 1.47 % developed eclampsia, and 22.05 % developed oligohydramnios. FGR was

seen in 42.64 %, placental abruption in 4.41% and stillbirth in 5.88 %. The number of antenatal women who developed pregnancy complications and adverse outcomes in the second trimester of pregnancy was 33.8%.

In present study, among 28 subjects with $PI \geq 1.5$, Adverse pregnancy outcomes was present in 15 females (53.57%) and in remaining 13 subjects (46.43%) it was not present. In 72 subjects with $PI < 1.5$, Adverse pregnancy outcomes was present in 18 subjects (25%) and in remaining 54 women (75%) it was absent. There was a statistically significant difference between the two ($p < 0.01$). Among 28 subjects with $PI \geq 1.5$, Gestational hypertension was present in 3 females (10.71%), Preeclampsia in 4 women (14.29%), one subjects (3.57%) each had Eclampsia, Placental abruption, Stillbirth and Mortality; 8 (28.57%) had FGR and 5 (17.86%) had Oligohydramnios. In 72 subjects with $PI < 1.5$, one subject (1.39%) each Gestational hypertension, Oligohydramnios and Stillbirth; 2 females (2.78%) had Preeclampsia; and Fetal growth

restriction (FGR) was present in 5 subjects (6.94). There was statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$) in Gestational hypertension, Preeclampsia, Oligohydramnios and FGR when two groups were compared.

Out of the 100 subjects involved in study, notching was present in 24 subjects, and in remaining 76 it was not present. Jayson JA et al., (2021), found in their study that number of antenatal women who were primigravida was 45 % and 26.2% of them developed abnormal Doppler's in the first trimester of pregnancy. The number of antenatal women with abnormal first trimester Doppler who developed at least one of the pregnancy complications and adverse outcomes was 40%. It was also observed that 19 % of women with normal uterine artery Doppler findings of first trimester developed pregnancy complications and adverse outcomes.

Among 28 subjects with $PI \geq 1.5$, 3 neonates (10.71%) were underweight, and 5 (17.86%) required NICU admission; whereas there was no mortality. In 72 subjects with $PI < 1.5$, only 1 neonate (1.39%) required NICU admission. There was statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$) when neonatal outcome i.e., underweight child and neonate which required NICU admission was compared among subjects with $PI \geq 1.5$ and females with $PI < 1.5$. Jayson JA et al., (2021) [8], results showed that FGR was high (20%) in the women who had abnormal first trimester uterine artery pulsatility index, when compared to 7% of women who had normal uterine artery Doppler. Therefore, p value was significant, which was 0.0022.

According to PI, Sensitivity was 63.80%, Specificity was 82.40%, Negative Predictive Value (NPV) was 60.60%, Positive Predictive Value (PPV) was 80.90% and Accuracy was 68.2%. This shows that PI can help in prediction of preeclampsia. Jayson JA et al., (2021), found that the sensitivity of first trimester uterine artery pulsatility index was 42.03% and specificity was 80.57%. The positive predictive value was 41.43% and negative predictive value was 80.95%. Bindal J, Chugh N (2016) [9] found in their study that out of 100 patients, 15% had PI of > 1.71 at 11-14 weeks of pregnancy out of that 12 (80%) developed preeclampsia hence sensitivity of PI is 54.54 % and specificity is 96.15%, PPV 85 %, NPV 88 % in prediction of preeclampsia.

Conclusion

According to the results of the current study, uterine artery color Doppler is a useful and non-invasive method for predicting preeclampsia at term in healthy pregnancies. In pregnancies without

any additional risk factors, the presence of a diastolic notch and a PI value of ≥ 1.5 during 11–14 weeks of gestation serve as a reliable indicator of preeclampsia at term. Therefore, around 11 to 14 weeks of pregnancy, all high risk pregnancies should be checked with a uterine artery doppler to detect instances that could develop preeclampsia and to implement early measures to prevent and lessen the severity of the condition. By allowing for the early detection and close monitoring of women with at-risk pregnancies, can help in early accurate assessment of preeclampsia risk, which in turn would significantly save antenatal care expenditures and enhance the management of hypertension illnesses in later life and decreasing maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality.

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